

Research Article

**A Descriptive Case Study on the Rising Incidence of the Squamous
Cell carcinoma of the Head and Neck Region**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The squamous cell carcinoma of Head and neck is the most common malignancy of head and neck. It accounts for around 22% of total burden of cancers of the Asian countries.

Method: It is descriptive type of case study.

SETTING: This study was done at department of surgery DHQ Hospital Sargodha. 98 patients were enrolled and Biopsies taken which then sent for histopathology.

Inclusion Criteria: Primary disease, mucosal disease.

Exclusion Criteria: Children mentally retarded, congenital tumors.

Objective: The objective of this study was to determine the risk of factors, sites involved in order to promote the education of the community for better prevention of the disease. The mean age of patients is 51 ± 9.31 years the enrolled 55% of patients were male and 45% females. Among the cases enrolled for the study, 66% were from urban areas and 34% belonged to rural areas.

Conclusion: Head and Neck squamous carcinoma is the most common form of tumor in Head and Neck region. The most common site is hypopharynx and the most important risk factor is smoking. The highest incidence of the disease in 5th decade. Head and Neck tumor comprises Neoplastic growth of the oral cavity including Nasal cavity, Pharyngeal cavity, salivary glands, lips and Paranasal sinuses. HNC (head and neck carcinoma) comprises 6% of total tumors of the world. 110,000 patients are diagnosed with HNC in Europe/year.

INTRODUCTION

Head and neck cancers are classified together with justification of epidemiology, Risk factors, similar natural history, control measures and morphology. Squamous cell carcinoma is the most common of all accounting for 22% of Asian burden of cancers. A study Locally done on the trends of the cancer patients shows 2 years' survival rate to be 71% diagnosed between 2012-2016. Another study shows the 2 years' average survival rate to be 63%. Another study done a few years back in Mayo hospital reported the average 2-year

survival rate to be 71%. it may be variable depending on the stage and grade of the disease.

Methodology: It was a descriptive cross-sectional study of retrospective type.

Sample size: 98 patients were enrolled in the study biopsies were taken and sent to histopathology lab for diagnosis and squamous cell carcinoma was reported.

Duration: The study was done from July 16-March 17.

Data was taken about gender, age, and smoking history. Histological diagnoses were acquired from the pathology lab. Data was compiled and analyzed by SPSS 19. Means were taken for quantitative variables and percentage were taken for qualitative variables.

Results: Mean age of patients is 51 ± 9.31 . Median age is 54 years. Mean age of females was 45.73 ± 3.32 .

56% patients were from rural areas and 44% were from urban side. Smoking history was present in 58% of cases while 23% suffered from iron deficiency among 5% the history positive for Pan chewing and 5% were Alcoholics. Rest of the cases showed No identifiable cause. Females from the villages suffered slightly more than urban areas females may be due to nutritional deficiency. On histopathology it was revealed that 57% patients had well differentiated carcinoma while 21% suffered from moderately differentiated and 22% showed poor differentiation on histopathology.

DISCUSSION:

The Head and Neck malignancies have different incidences in different parts of the world[1].

Pakistan is among the countries having high incidence for this disease due to increased Betel Nut, Pan chewing and smoking[2]. Our study shows almost same proportion of males and females who suffered from the disease. The most common site for the cancer is hypopharynx. Another study done in Lahore shows the same ratio of Females to males and the most common site was reported to be hypopharynx in their study[3].

A study in India Bihar, shows Hypo pharyngeal carcinoma to be the third most common carcinoma our study shows larynx to be the 2nd commonest site of carcinoma head and neck[4]. While another study done at Multan shows Larynx is the most common site of Head and Neck malignancies[5].

In our study it is reported that the females presented earlier as compared to their counterparts in age with the disease probably due to poor nutritional statuses of the females in our country.

The areas having increased betel Nut use and tobacco smoking have increased Risk of HNC[6]. Our study shows 10% of cases of cancer have oral cavity or oro-Pharyngeal tumors. While another study done in Africa shows HNC constitute 88% of cancer burden[7].

Conclusion: Pakistan falls in the category of high risk for Head and Neck malignancies. It is due to Not up to mark health education of patients. Risk factors like smoking, betel Nut, Pan chewing and malnutrition are increasing the burden of the disease. moreover, Late presentation and Non-Optimum treatment are the causes for the poor prognosis of the patients. proper health education and up to mark health care must be given to patients to put a control on the rising incidence of Head and neck carcinoma.

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